

VeriFish

The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns

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D4.3 – Documentation of the consensus-driven CWA process

Work Package	WP4 Develop a European Good Practice recommendation (CWA) for how to communicate on seafood
Task	T4.3 Stakeholder consultation campaigns towards a European Good Practice recommendation
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Peer reviewers	
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Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
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Keywords

VeriFish, seafood, consumer, communication, seafood types, seafood consumers, consumer types, communication strategies, fisheries, fishery, wild catch, wild harvest, aquaculture, farmed seafood

Disclaimer

VeriFish offers a framework of verifiable sustainability indicators for communications about sustainability based on FAIR data from EU- and global aquafoods repositories, brought together through the extraordinary collaboration of European-wide actors. Leveraging on this indicator, VeriFish designs, develops, and disseminates a number of media products to help citizens, seafood consumers and retailers, associations and policy makers make informed consumption choices.

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Executive Summary

The VeriFish Good Practice recommendation is intended as a practical tool for actors involved in seafood communication and marketing, supporting the design of campaigns that engage consumers more effectively. This recommendation is published as a low-level, voluntary European standard which will be distributed by the European Committee for Standardization (CEN) as a CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA). The CWA is designed to help the seafood industry communicate with consumers about their products, and the aim is to support an increase in sustainable seafood consumption.

This report *D4.3 – “Documentation of the consensus-driven CWA process”* is linked to task 4.3 – “Stakeholder consultation campaigns towards a European Good Practice recommendation” within VeriFish and describes the CWA process in some detail, with documents, procedures, and participants. This document accompanies D4.2 – “Good Practice Recommendation” which describes the outcome of the CWA process; the CWA itself.

The content of this document are the details around how the CWA process was organised. A key component is the “Workshop Description Form” which has to be filled in by the workshop proposer (VeriFish) and accepted by CEN and the secretariat; this form is in Annex A. The agenda for the kick-off meeting can be found in Annex B, and the minutes of the kick-off meeting can be found in Annex C. The official version of all these documents can be found on the web page set up by CEN for the VeriFish CWA at: <https://www.cencenelec.eu/news-events/news/2025/workshop/2025-05-19-verifish/>

The goal of a CWA process is to achieve consensus, and for VeriFish we managed this. On the beginning of the process there was a lot of discussion and some disagreement on scope and direction for the Good Practice recommendation, but as new drafts were made based on comments received, a common understanding of what the CWA should contain developed, and discussions were on minor issues only. At the consensus meeting none of the participants opted out of the process due to disagreement with the recommendations, which seems to indicate that the goal of the process was reached.

TABLE OF CONTENT

Introduction	4
1 The VeriFish CWA	5
2 The VeriFish CWA schedule.....	6
3 The VeriFish CWA participants.....	7
Appendix I – The Workshop Description Form	9
CEN Workshop VeriFish	9
PART A – Workshop Summary.....	10
PART B – Project Plan.....	12
Appendix II – Agenda for the kick-off meeting	19
Appendix III – Minutes from the kick-off meeting.....	20

Introduction

The VeriFish CWA provides Good Practice recommendations on how to effectively engage and influence different consumer groups to encourage sustainable seafood consumption. Rather than defining concepts such as “local”, “seasonal”, “nutritious”, or “healthy”, this document focuses on how such attributes can be communicated more effectively. The recommendations aim to support the design of targeted seafood communication and marketing campaigns by ensuring that relevant, verifiable content is presented in ways that are more likely to influence purchasing behaviour.

The target audience for the CWA includes public and private organisations involved in the design or implementation of seafood communication or promotion campaigns. It is intended to support actors seeking guidance on how to prioritise messages and communication approaches based on specific seafood products and target consumer groups. The initiative responds to an expressed need from seafood stakeholders and communicators across Europe for practical, harmonised guidance in this field.

The CWA can be found in VeriFish deliverable D4.2 – “Good Practice Recommendation” and after project end it will be published by CEN as a CWA available through national standardization bodies. This document describes the details of the CWA process, including:

- What a CWA is, and why we made one
- What the schedule for the VeriFish CWA was
- Who the participants were
- The Workshop Description Form which is the agreement between the workshop proposers (VeriFish, represented by Nofima) and CEN on scope, content, and schedule for the CWA process
- The official agenda for the CWA kick-off meeting, published at the CEN website for the VeriFish Workshop
- The official minutes from the CWA kick-off meeting, published at the CEN website for the VeriFish Workshop

There were two hearing periods and many other meetings and minutes in the process, but they were informal in nature so records of these have not been included here.

1 The VeriFish CWA

This is how the VeriFish CWA is described in the VeriFish Description of Action (DoA):

The VeriFish CWA is a low-level, voluntary European standard (a CEN Workshop Agreement or CWA) containing “Good Practice” recommendations on how to efficiently engage and influence various types of consumers to encourage consumption of local, seasonal, nutritious, healthy, and sustainable seafood. The target group for this recommendation is any public or private organization who is in the process of launching a “eat more seafood” campaign, and who wants to get advice on what to focus on, given the seafood and the consumer group in question. The reasons for providing this recommendation as a European standard rather than as a project report or similar are many, and includes:

- A CWA will live and be an active and available document for 3-6 years after the project has finished
- A CWA is distributed by CEN which is an independent organization
- A CWA has (literally) a standard format and structure
- A CWA is consensus-based and requires open, publicly announced meetings and a hearing period
- A CWA process also receives input from stakeholders outside the project
- A CWA will reach target groups that the project couldn’t engage directly, also after project end
- A CWA can serve as a de facto standard to support normative and commercial certification schemes for social responsibility and others.; a CWA can later form the basis for a higher level standard

The methodology for making a CWA has been formalised by CEN (The European Committee for Standardization) and is designed to be suitable for EC funded projects. Briefly the steps are as follows:

1. Fill in a CWA proposal form and a draft project plan, find a national standards body that is willing to act as secretariat. Traditionally, for standards relating to fish and seafood, Standard Norway acts as the secretariat.
2. Check that the proposed CWA is not in violation of existing CEN standards; get acceptance from CEN Technical Board.
3. Public announcement (by CEN and by the CWA participants) of a new CEN Workshop, at least 30 days before designated public kick-off meeting; open for anyone to register and participate.

4. Produce draft content, discuss, get input, update draft content of CWA. Facilitate hearing periods, process input, aim for consensus.
5. After normally about 12 months, public announcement (by CEN and by the CWA participants) at least 30 days before the event of a final consensus meeting where the final recommendations are presented and discussed. There is no voting process; those that agree with the recommendations can be listed as contributors.
6. Publication of the CWA by CEN, maintained and distributed by CEN for at least 3, normally at least 6, years. The published CWA will be distributed and maintained (and updated if necessary) by the national standards organization that acts as secretariat and in addition by any other European national standards bodies that indicate interest; normally at in at least a handful of countries.

Publishing the recommendation as a CWA in no way limits the distribution of the improved methods or the project results in any way. After the CWA standardization process has finished CEN will have exclusive rights on distributing the official CWA document. However, the content of the CWA (which is basically everything except the first and last pages of the CWA document), is still owned by the project, and can be distributed freely.

The CWA process has been employed successfully in previous EU seafood projects, including in CSAs, and has frequently led to subsequent implementation or formal standards. Examples include:

- EU 5FP TraceFish, where the CWAs developed in the project formed the basis for the ISO 12875 / 12877 “Traceability of finfish products ...” standards
- EU 6FP WhiteFish, where “CWA 16960:2015 – Batch-based Calculation of Sustainability Impact for Captured Fish Products” has formed the basis for calculation of environmental impact from fishing vessels
- H2020 ClimeFish, where “CWA 17518:2020 – Good practice recommendations for making Climate Adaptation Plans for fisheries and aquaculture” has formed the basis of marine resource management plans and has been referred to in policy documents.

2 The VeriFish CWA schedule

- April/May 2025, filled in and submitted the Workshop Description Form for the VeriFish CWA
- May 19th 2025, official launch of the CEN Workshop “VeriFish”, as documented on <https://www.cencenelec.eu/news-events/news/2025/workshop/2025-05-19-verifish/>

- June 24th 2025, kick-off meeting (physical) in Copenhagen for the VeriFish CWA where an initial draft (Draft V0) was presented and discussed
- Summer 2025, updated Draft V0 with comments from the kick-off meeting, made Draft V1
- August 2025, hearing period for Draft V1
- Fall 2025, updated Draft V1 with comments from the hearing period, made Draft V2
- December 2025 / January 2026, hearing period for Draft V2
- February 2026, updated Draft V2 with comments from the hearing period, made Draft V3
- March 10th 2026, consensus meeting (physical) in Brussels for the VeriFish CWA where Draft V3 was presented and discussed
- April 2026, updated Draft V3 with comments from the consensus meeting, made the final version of the VeriFish CWA
- April 2026, sent the final version of the VeriFish CWA to CEN for publication

3 The VeriFish CWA participants

When the VeriFish CWA was sent to CEN for publishing, the list of registered participants was as follows:

Clupea	Christine Absil
Clupea	Michelle Boonstra
COMMpla	Alessandro Petrocelli
Cromaris d.d.	Tamara Tarnik
EATIP	David Bassett
EC	Pilar Roman
EFFOP	Gaëtane Le Brueil
EFFOP	Jame Hinchcliffe
EuroCommerce	Sarah Hautier
EUROFIR	Paul Finglas
EUROFIR	Sian Astley
EuroFish	Francesca Barazzetta
EuroFish	Ixai Salvo
EuroFish	Marco Frederiksen
EuroFish	Toni Bartulin
Europêche	Rosalie Tukker

FAO	Anton Ellenbroek
Federación Regional de Cofradías de Pescadores de Canarias	Enrique Sánchez-Fabrés
FISH.COOP.FRIŠKA RIBA P.O.	Linda Zanki Duvnjak
FORTH	Yannis Marketakis
ICES	Anne Marie Cooper
Independent	Alessandro Manghisi
Lantern innovation	Regina Llorente Suarez
MGF3.0	Hélène Buisson
Moceans Environmental Consultants	Momo Kochen
Nofima	Oda Bjørnsborg
Nofima	Petter Olsen
Nofima	Roy Robertsen
Nofima	Silje Steinsbø
Nofima	Themis Altintzoglou
Oceana	Marine Cusa
OPAGAC	Jorge López
PMT	Karl Presser
PMT	Malwina Cieśła
Poseidon	Tim Huntington
Poseidon	Tracy Murai
Submariner	Efthalia Arvaniti
Trust-IT	Sabrina Duri
Trust-IT	Sara Pittonet Gaiarin
University of Galway	Bernadete Rodrigues
West Pomeranian University of Technology in Szczecin	Piotr Eljasik

Contributors have the option of removing their name from the final publication, so this list might not match what is indicated in the official VeriFish CWA published by CEN after VeriFish ends.

Appendix I – The Workshop Description Form

CEN Workshop VeriFish

Workshop description form

- PART A – Workshop Summary
- PART B – Project Plan

PART A – Workshop Summary

1	WS details	
1.1.	Organization	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> CEN <input type="checkbox"/> CENELEC <input type="checkbox"/> Joint with <input type="checkbox"/> CEN lead <input type="checkbox"/> CENELEC lead
1.2.	Title	CEN Workshop VeriFish
1.3.	Scope	Good Practice recommendation on how to efficiently communicate to consumers about seafood
1.4.	Does this WS stem from an EU Research project?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> YES Name of the project: VeriFish Grant number: Horizon Europe #101156426 End date 30/04/26 <input type="checkbox"/> NO
1.5.	Financial support	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EU Research project <input type="checkbox"/> EC/EFTA Grant reference: Type here <input type="checkbox"/> Other Specify, if needed: Type here
1.6.	WS Proposer/Proposed Chair WS proposer	Name: Petter Olsen Organization: Nofima Postal address: Muninbakken 9-13 Email: Petter.olsen@nofima.no Phone: +4790698303 Webpage: www.nofima.no Contact person (name and email): Petter Olsen, petter.olsen@nofima.no
1.7.	WS Secretariat	Organization: Standard Norge Postal address: P.O. Box 242, NO-1326 Lysaker, Norway Email: info@standard.no Phone: +47 67 83 86 01 Webpage: https://standard.no/en/ WS Secretary name: Camilla Haugen Email: chau@standard.no Phone: +47 92 26 88 68
1.8.	CEN and CENELEC Management Centre (CCMC) contact	Organization: CEN and CENELEC Postal address: Rue de la Science 23B - 1040 Brussels, Belgium Webpage: https://www.cenelec.eu/Pages/default.aspx CCMC Project Manager name: Claire Van Thielen Email: cwa@cenelec.eu Phone: +3225500831 +32478793545
1.9.	Tentative date and place of the Kick-off Meeting	Date: 2025-06-24 Place: DG Byen, Copenhagen

1.10.	Does the proposed Workshop fall within the scope of existing CEN and/or CENELEC Technical Bodies? ¹	<input type="checkbox"/>	YES Specify	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO
1.11.	Are there other Technical Bodies or Joint Advisory and Coordination Groups potentially interested in the Workshop? ²	<input type="checkbox"/>	YES Specify: Type here	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO
1.12.	Are the following aspects affected?	Safety matters Management system aspects Conformity assessment aspects Security matters		YES ³ <input type="checkbox"/> YES ⁴ <input type="checkbox"/> YES ⁵ <input type="checkbox"/> YES ⁶ <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 7 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NO <input type="checkbox"/> 8
		Add information/explanations if Management System aspects and Conformity Assessment aspects are affected: Type here			
2 WS Deliverables					
2.1.	CWA #1				
2.1.1	Title	<input type="checkbox"/>	Same as WS title (1.2)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Other: Good Practice recommendation on how to efficiently communicate to consumers about seafood
2.1.2	Scope		Good Practice recommendation on how to efficiently communicate to consumers about seafood		
2.1.3	Does the proposed CWA conflict with a published EN	<input type="checkbox"/>	YES Specify: Type here	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	NO In case the answer is 'yes', the development of the CWA shall be stopped

PART B – Project Plan

1) Abstract

The VeriFish CWA is a low-level, voluntary European standard (a CEN Workshop Agreement or CWA) containing “Good Practice” recommendations on how to efficiently engage and influence various types of consumers to encourage consumption of local, seasonal, nutritious, healthy, and sustainable seafood. The target group for this recommendation is any public or private organization who is in the process of launching a “eat more seafood” campaign, and who wants to get advice on what to focus on, given the seafood and the consumer group in question.

2) Status of the project plan

Draft project plan for public commenting (Version 1.0)

This draft project plan is intended to inform the public of a new Workshop. Any interested party can take part in this Workshop and/or comment on this draft project plan by sending an email to the WS secretary.

All those who have applied for participation or have commented on the project plan by the deadline will be invited to the kick-off meeting of the Workshop on 2025-06-24.

3) Workshop proposer and potential Workshop participants

3.1 Workshop proposer

Person (and organization): Petter Olsen, Nofima

Short description and interest in the subject:

Petter Olsen has a Dr.philos in food traceability from University of Tromsø, Norway, 2017 and has worked at Nofima since 1993, currently as Senior Scientist at the department for Industrial Economics. Works with applications of ICT in the food industry, especially related to information logistics, traceability, IoT, blockchain technology, authenticity, fraud, production management, simulation, sustainability and decision support systems. Adjunct professor at UiT, the Arctic University of Norway, teaching courses on traceability, information logistics, and proposal writing. Serves as an adviser to FAO, EFSA, WWF, the EC, and several EU-funded projects on these subjects. Coordinator of the EU projects TraceFish (5FP), WhiteFish (7FP), and OCCAM (HE), and WP leader in several dozen other European, Nordic, and national projects. Author or co-author of 7 European standards (EN 17972 and 6 CWAs), 2 ISO standards (ISO 12875 and 12877) and more than 25 peer-refereed scientific publications. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9411-6271>.

3.2 Potential participants

This CWA will be developed in a Workshop (temporary body) that is open to any interested party. The participation of the following persons/organizations would be helpful and is desired. It is recommended that:

- Seafood producing companies, especially SMEs
- Seafood industry organizations
- Seafood traders and retailers
- Scientists working with seafood marketing and consumer behaviour
- Scientists in international research projects focusing on increasing consumption of seafood, in particular the Horizon Europe projects Mr.Goodfish3.0: “Co-creating solutions for sustainable seafood consumption” and VeriFish “The sustainability indicator framework to communicate responsible aquafood production and consumption patterns”.

take part in the development of this CWA.

4) Workshop objectives and scope

4.1 Workshop background

The VeriFish CWA will contain “Good Practice” recommendations on how to efficiently engage and influence various types of consumers to encourage consumption of local, seasonal, nutritious, healthy, and sustainable seafood. The target group for this recommendation is any public or private organization who is in the process of launching a “eat more seafood” campaign, and who wants to get advice on what to focus on, given the seafood and the consumer group in question. Seafood stakeholders and communicators have expressed a need for a Good Practice recommendation in this field, and this initiative is connected to a large variety of European organizations and initiatives that communicate about seafood. The immediate goal is for seafood marketing campaigns to be more efficient, and to reach more consumers with messages that will influence buying behaviour. This means that for a given budget, campaigns can cast a wider net, target more consumer groups and cultures, and be more specific with the message communicated to the target groups. The long-term goal is for consumers to eat more sustainable seafood, and for producers and retailers to sell more sustainable seafood.

5) Workshop programme

5.1 General

The kick-off meeting is planned to take place on 2025-06-24 at location DG Byen in Copenhagen. A draft for public commenting will be distributed to those who register for the meeting.

A total of 2 physical meetings and 3 virtual meetings will be held, during which the content of the CWA(s) will be presented, discussed and approved.

The working language (language of meetings, minutes, etc.) of the WS will be **English**. The CWA will be written in **English**.

5.2 Workshop schedule

Table 1: Workshop schedule

CEN/CENELEC Workshop	May25	Jun25	Jul25	Aug25	Sep25	Oct25	Nov25	Dec25	Jan26	Feb26	Mar 6	Apr26
Initiation	█											
1. Workshop description form submission and TC response	█	█										
2. Open commenting period on draft project plan (mandatory)		█	█									
Operation		█										
3. Kick-off meeting – Consensus meeting			█								█	
4. CWA(s) development	█	█	█	█	█		█	█				
5. Open commenting period on draft CWA(s) (optional)					█	█			█	█		
6. CWA(s) finalized and approved by Workshop											█	
participants												█
Publication												█
7. CWA(s) publication												█
Dissemination (see 6)	█	█	█		█			█				█
Milestones		K		V			V	V			M/A	P D

Legend

K: Kick-off, **M:** Workshop meeting, **V:** Virtual Workshop meeting, **A:** Adoption of CWA, **P:** Publication of CWA, **D:** Online distribution of CWA

6) Resource planning

All costs related to the participation of interested parties in the Workshop's activities have to be borne by themselves.

7) Workshop structure and rules of cooperation

7.1 Participation in the Workshop

The Workshop will be constituted during the kick-off meeting. By approving this project plan, the interested parties declare their willingness to participate in the Workshop and will be formally named as Workshop participants, with the associated rights and duties. Participants at the kick-off meeting who do not approve the project plan are not given the status of a Workshop participant and are thus excluded from further decisions made during the kick-off meeting and from any other decisions regarding the Workshop.

As a rule, the request to participate in the Workshop is closed once it is constituted. The current Workshop participants shall decide whether any additional members will be accepted or not.

Any new participant in the Workshop at a later date is decided on by the participants making up the Workshop at that time.

All Workshop participants who approved the publication of the CWA or its draft will be named as authors in the European Foreword, including the organizations which they represent. All Workshop participants who did not approve the publication of the CWA will not be named in the European Foreword.

7.2 Workshop responsibilities

The Workshop Chair is responsible for content management and consensus building. The Workshop Chair is supported by the Workshop Vice-Chair (if any) and the responsible Workshop secretariat, whereby the Workshop secretariat will always remain neutral regarding the content of the CWA(s). Furthermore, the Workshop secretariat shall ensure that CEN-CENELEC's rules of procedure, rules of presentation, and the principles governing the publication of CWA(s) have been observed. Should a Workshop Chair no longer be able to carry out her/his duties, the Workshop secretariat shall initiate the election of a new Workshop Chair. The list below covers the main tasks of the Workshop Chair. It is not intended to be exhaustive.

- Content related contact point for the Workshop
- Presides at Workshop meetings
- Ensures that the development of the CWA respects the principles and content of the adopted project plan
- Manages the consensus building process, assesses when the Workshop participants have reached agreement on the final CWA, on the basis of the comments received
- Ensures due information exchange with the Workshop secretariat

- Represents the Workshop and its results to exterior

The Workshop secretariat, provided by a CEN and/or CENELEC Member, is responsible for organizing and leading the kick-off meeting, in consultation with the Workshop proposer. Further Workshop meetings and/or web conferences shall be organized by the Workshop secretariat in consultation with the Workshop Chair. The list below covers the main tasks of the Workshop secretariat. It is not intended to be exhaustive.

- Administrative and organizational contact point for the Workshop
- Ensures that the development of the CWA respects the principles and content of the adopted project plan and of the requirements of the CEN-CENELEC Guide 29
- Formally registers Workshop participants and maintains record of participating organizations and individuals
- Offers infrastructure and manages documents and their distribution through an electronic platform
- Prepares agenda and distributes information on meetings and meeting minutes as well as follow-up actions of the Workshop
- Initiates and manages CWA approval process upon decision by the Workshop Chair
- Interfaces with CEN-CENELEC Management Centre (CCMC) and Workshop Chair regarding strategic directions, problems arising, and external relationships
- Advises on CEN-CENELEC rules and brings any major problems encountered (if any) in the development of the CWA to the attention of CEN-CENELEC Management Centre (CCMC)
- Administrates the connection with relevant CEN or CENELEC/TCs

7.3 Decision making process

The CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop Chair is responsible for ensuring that the development of the CWA follows the principles and content of the project plan described in this document and the requirements of CEN-CENELEC Guide 29. The CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop Chair may take decisions on the conduct of the CEN and/or CENELEC Workshop on the basis of the comments expressed by the participants and of CEN-CENELEC Guide 29.

Decisions shall be taken based on consensus of the WS participants.

8) Dissemination and participation strategy

Potential participants identified in section 2.2 and potential interested stakeholders identified in Part A will be informed of the open commenting phase, if any, and of the publication of the CWA.

In addition to the CCMC website, the final CWA will be advertised in sector-specific channels (EuroFish) and by through the wide networks established by the projects Mr.Goodfish3.0 and VeriFish. In addition, the organizations involved in these projects will advertise the CWA process and the existence of the final Good Practice recommendation on their websites, to their respective networks, and through social media. A LinkedIn group has already been set up.

Appendix II – Agenda for the kick-off meeting

Agenda for the kick-off meeting of CEN/WS VeriFish

Copenhagen, Denmark, Tuesday June 24th, 12:00-17:00 CEST

Venue: DGI Byen, Tietgensgade 65, 1704 Copenhagen, Denmark

Agenda	Timing
1. Opening of the meeting	12.00
2. Roll call of participants	12.10
3. Adoption of the agenda	12.30
4. Introduction on CEN and on the Workshop concept	12.40
5. Our experience with CWAs in RTD projects	12.50
6. General presentation of the Workshop	13.00
7. Presentation of our starting point, VeriFish “D4.1 – Initial recommendation for how to efficiently communicate to consumers about seafood”	13.10
8. Discussions on scope of the of CWA	13.30
9. Discussions on the structure of the CWA	14.00
10. Discussions on content of the CWA	14.30
11. Election and appointment of Workshop Chair, Confirmation of the Secretariat	15.50
12. Project Plan	
a. Discussion and review of comments received	16.00
b. Adoption of the Project Plan (by consensus)	16.20
13. Organization of the technical work	16.30
14. Any other business	16.40
15. Next meeting, future actions and their assignment	16.50
16. Closure of the meeting	17.00

Appendix III – Minutes from the kick-off meeting

CEN/WS VeriFish 'Kick-off meeting' Report of the meeting

Date of the meeting: 24-06-2025

Venue: DGI Byen, Tietgensgade 65, 1704 Copenhagen, Denmark

1. Opening of the meeting

The chairperson, Petter Olsen, welcomed the participants and opened the meeting at 12:00. The meeting was held face-to-face in person in Copenhagen, with some participants joining via Zoom. Exploitation rights were circulated and to be returned to Standards Norway representatives, Camilla Haugen and Johanne Knutsen, by the end of the meeting.

Sara gave a brief introduction to the indicator framework and approach of the VeriFish project. A central outcome of the project is the development of a CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA), which will contain recommendations and guidelines.

Petter informed the group that a consensus meeting will take place in Brussels at the end of the process. Participants will need to decide whether they wish to be listed as contributors/co-authors in the document. If not, they may still take part in the process and provide input.

2. Roll Call

A brief roll call was conducted, during which participants stated their names and affiliations. All participants are listed in Annex 1.

3. Approval of the agenda

The agenda was presented and approved with no further comments.

4. Introduction on CEN and on the Workshop concept

Claire Van Thielen (CCMC) presented an overview of CEN/CENELEC and the CWA development process (see N01). She also referred to the Code of Conduct, see link for more information: [Code of Conduct](#)

5. Our experience with CWAs in RTD projects

Petter Olsen shared his previous experiences with the development of CWAs, noting that some have later been further developed into ISO standards.

6. Presentation of our starting point, VeriFish “D4.1 – Initial recommendation for how to efficiently communicate to consumers about seafood”

Petter presented the document "VeriFish D4.1," addressing the marketing challenges faced by small and medium-sized enterprises in the seafood sector. The document aims to provide effective communication strategies towards consumers and support increased seafood consumption.

7. Discussions on scope of the of CWA

The document is intended for a business-to-consumer (B2C) audience. A two-level categorization structure for seafood was presented:

- Level 1: Differentiation between products from *fishery* and *aquaculture* sources.
- Level 2: Distinction between products that *require preparation* and those that are *ready to eat*.

It was emphasized that the communication approach for seafood products should remain consistent, and that legislation serves as the baseline requirement.

The group reached a common understanding of the structure reflected in Table 1 (p. 19, see N02). The forthcoming CWA will highlight the positive aspects of the identified characteristics.

The following topics were considered outside the scope of the work and thus excluded:

- Dietary supplements and oils
- Guidance on product claims

8. Discussions on the structure/content of the CWA

It was agreed that the definition “anything edible from the aquatic environment, including plants – for human consumption. Products consumed by humans for food” should encompass anything edible from the aquatic environment, including plants such as seaweed, provided it is intended for human consumption. It was suggested that this wording be included in the introduction of the document. Further, it was proposed to expand the definition of “seafood” either in the introduction or in Chapter 3 (Definitions). The term *seafood* was discussed and defined as covering all aquatic organisms, including

freshwater species and edible aquatic plants such as seaweed.

The following consumer categories were considered but decided not to be included due to limited information or relevance at this stage:

- Vegans
- Price-sensitive consumers (owing to insufficient data for meaningful inclusion)

The group also discussed consumers preferring locally sourced products, considering how this aspect could be reflected in the framework. Additionally, it was suggested to highlight differences in nutritional value between fresh and raw fish.

Further, the group discussed the two-level categorization of seafood presented in Table 1 (p. 19, see N02).

At Level 1, the categories “Fishery” and “Aquaculture” were retained as the main distinction. It was noted that this terminology aligns with usage in EU legislation and policy frameworks. Alternative categorizations, such as those based on production systems, trophic levels, or fishing methods, were considered but ultimately not included.

The group emphasized that the understanding of quality-conscious consumers may vary across cultures and contexts, and that definitions of quality should be consistent with EU frameworks. Additionally, it was agreed to include “catch area” as a characteristic relevant to health-conscious consumers.

At Level 2, the categorization distinguishes between seafood products that require preparation and those that are ready for consumption. This approach reflects how products may be presented or communicated in consumer-facing contexts. Alternative proposals, such as distinguishing between fresh and processed products, were discussed but not adopted.

Finally, the HORECA sector (hotels, restaurants, and catering) was recognized as an important audience group to be reflected in the main body of the document.

9. Election and appointment of Workshop Chair, confirmation of the secretariat

Petter raised the question if anyone would consider taking the role as chair for the workshop. As no one volunteered for the role Petter agreed to do it. The secretariat was also presented and confirmed with Standards Norway and Johanne Knutsen as the secretary.

10. Project Plan

a) Discussion and review of comments received There were no comments received leading up to the meeting.

b) Adoption of the Project Plan (by consensus)

The projectplan (see N03) and schedule was presented step by step.

11. Organization of the technical work

It was agreed to put down a task group to write the drafts. The following participants will take part in the task group:

From VeriFish:

- Silje Steinsbø (Nofima)
- Siân Astley (EuroFIR)
- Sara Pittonet Gaiarin (Trust-IT)
- Ixai Salvo (Eurofish)

Others:

- Marine Cusa (Oceana)

12. Any other business

No further business was brought up.

13. Next meeting, future actions and their assignment

A new document will be circulated and there will be a commenting period from august 8th. By the end of august the task group will resume the work on the document and prepare a draft for a new commenting round.

When the document is circulated on August 8th everyone will also receive a commenting template. There will be more information on how to register comments.

14. Closure of the meeting

Petter thanked everyone for participating at the Kick-Off meeting. The meeting closed at 17:00 pm.